

A Study of Women Entrepreneurship in India

K.Santhiya

I-MBA, Department of Business Administration, Annai Women's College, Karur

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V.Monisha

I-MBA, Department of Business Administration, Annai Women's College, Karur

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Abstract

The educated Indian women have to go a long way to achieve equal rights and position because traditions are intensely rooted in Indian society where the sociological set up has been a male dominated one. Despite all the social obstacles, Indian women stand tall from the rest of the mass and are commended for their activities in their respective field. The transformation of social fabric of the Indian society, in terms the increased educational status of women and varied ambitions for better living, required a change in the lifestyle of Indian women. Women have disputed with man and successfully stood up with him in every walk of life and business is no exception for this. These women leaders are self-assured, winning and willing to take risks. They managed to live and succeed in this cut brawl with their hard work, concentration and persistence. This study released the study of women entrepreneurship in India.

Keywords: Women, Entrepreneur, society, socio- economics, Qualities.

Introduction

A woman or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Any woman or group of women, which innovates, initiates or adapts an economic activity is called "women entrepreneurship".

Women constitute around half of the total world population. So is in India also. The Indian women enjoy a disadvantageous status in the society. Let some facts are given. The much low literacy rate (40%), low work participation rate (28%) and low city population share (10%) of women as compared to 60%, 52% and 18% correspondingly of their male counterparts well confirm their disadvantageous position in the society.

A sense towards independent decision-making on their life and career is the motivational factor behind this urge. Burdened with household chores and domestic responsibilities women want to get independence. Under the influence of these factors the women entrepreneurs choose a occupation as a challenge and as an urge to do some thing new. Such a situation is described as pull factors. While in push factors women involved in business activities due to family pressure and the responsibility is push upon them.

There has been a significant growth in self-employment of women with women now starting new ventures at three times the rate of men. They constitute 50% of the population of our country with a lower literacy rate than men. In the traditional society they were confined to the four walls, playing household roles, but in the modern society, they are coming out to participate in all sorts of activities.

Objectives

- The main aim of the conceptual study is to list out the qualities need to women entrepreneur.
- It also aims to discuss the various types of women entrepreneur.
- It finds out the causes for slow improvement of women entrepreneurs
- It disclose the problems of women entrepreneurs theoretical manner
- It also discussed about ideas for the growth of women entrepreneurs

Qualities Need to Women Entrepreneur

The Women entrepreneurs must have some qualities to success in their business ventures. Some qualities of women entrepreneurs are given in below:

- Enthusiastic
- Realistic
- Optimistic
- Developmental
- Self-confident
- Self-motivation
- Solving problems
- Courage
- Imaginative

Classification of Women Entrepreneurs

According to Robert Goffee and Richard Scase women entrepreneurs are classified into four types.

1. Innovative Entrepreneurs

The Innovative entrepreneurs want to prove through their own situation that work or professional development is more important than conservative female roles. These Innovative Entrepreneurs want reach certified goals in their personal companies.

2. Radicals-Proprietors

The Radical entrepreneurs are dynamic in economic and political schemes that strongly help female issues. They do not care as much for profit-making as “INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURS”, their motivation is to backer for the long term development of women intereststs.

3. Conventional Entrepreneurs

These Conventional women are not close to traditional female roles, differ from “INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURS” in the fact that they do not necessarily existent dislike about limited career chances in previous jobs. In fact, they might have trained secondary jobs in the past and they might have changed from job several times.

4. Domestic Entrepreneurs

The Domestic women, even freelancing and entrepreneurs, see their businesses as secondary to their roles as mothers and wives, for occasion. “DOMESTICS” are not bad at all, in the end, work-life balance is not only important, but sustainable.

Some Women Entrepreneurs in India

There are many women entrepreneurs in our country. The following persons are some women entrepreneurs in India.

1. Indhu Jain-chairperson of India's largest media group, Bennett, coleman & co.,Ltd.,
2. Kiran Mazumdar Shaw-Founder Chairman and MD of Biocon Limited.
3. Indra Nooyi-CFO and President of PepsiCo.
4. Chanda Kochar-MD and CEO of ICICI Bank.
5. Falguni Nayar-MD of Kotak Mahindra Capita Company

Causes for Slow Improvement of Women Entrepreneurs

The major difficulties faced by women entrepreneurs are:

The greatest advice to women entrepreneurs is that they are women. A kind of male dominant social order is the building block to them in their way towards business success.

Male members think it a big risk financing the ventures run by women. In a male dominated society, women are not preserved equal to men that act as a barrier to woman's entry into business.

Women entrepreneurs have to face a hard competition with the men entrepreneurs who easily involve in the upgrade and development area and carry out easy marketing of their products with both the organized sector and their male complements.

Lack of self-confidence, will-power, strong mental outlook and positive attitude among women creates a fear from committing mistakes while doing their part of work. The family members and the society are unclear to stand beside their entrepreneurial growth.

The old and outdated social outlook to stop women from entering in the field of entrepreneurship is one of the causes for their failure. They are under a social stress which contains them to grow and attain success in the field of entrepreneurship

Unlike men, women flexibility in India is highly limited due to many reasons. A single women asking for room is still looked with doubt. Weighty exercise involved in starting with an enterprise coupled with officials degrading attitude towards women compels them to give up their spirit of living in enterprise.

Women's family obligations also bar them from becoming successful entrepreneurs in both developed and developing nations. The financial institutions discourage women entrepreneurs on the belief that they can at any time leave their business and become housewives again.

Indian women give more importance to family links and relationships. Married women have to make a fine balance between business and family. The business success also based on the support the family members extended to women in the business development and management.

Problems of Women Entrepreneurs

1. Family problems

In India, it is mainly a woman's duty to look after thr children and other members of the family. Her total involvement in family leaves little or no energy and time to devote for business. Women are expected to spend more time with their amily members. They do not encourage women to travel extensively for exploiting business opportunities.

2. Finance problems

The Family members do not encourage women entrepreneurs. They hesitate to invest money in the business started by women entrepreneurs. Bank and other Financial Institutions do not imitate Middle Class Women Entrepreneurs as correct applicants for setting up their projects and they are uncertain to provide financial assistance to unmarried women or girls as they are unconfident as to who will refund the loan.

3. Discrimination

Women is denied not in terms of her relation to man. Due to this social environment prevalent, they are unable to move independently as ast as an individual to distant places to mobilise their resources or markets.

4. Role Conflict

Marriage and family life are given more importance than occupation and social life for women in Indian society.

5. Unfavorable Environment

The society is dominated by males. Many business men are not interested to have business relationship with women entrepreneurs. Male generally do not encourage women entrepreneurs.

6. Gender Related

The women entrepreneurs are facing many Gender related problems in their life.

- A) Poor self image of woman
- B) Discrimination
- C) Faculty socialization
- D) Cultural values

7. Shortage of raw-materials

Women entrepreneurs encounter the problems of shortage of raw-materials. The failure of many women co-operations in 1971 such as these engaged in basket making were mainly because of the insufficient availability of forest-based raw materials.

8. Lack of Education

Due to lack of education and that too qualitative education, women are not aware of business, technology and market knowledge. In our country 60% of women are still illiterate.

9. Environmental Problems

The business men are not having business relationship with women because the society is dominated by men. Generally male do not support and encourage the women entrepreneurs.

10.Social recognition

The society does not give due recognition to women entrepreneurs. They are looked down as small and weak. Because of the above above reasons, the enterprises of women faces many problems in finance, marketing and expansion, etc.

Ideas for the Growth of Women Entrepreneurs

Right efforts from all areas are required in the development of women entrepreneurs and their greater participation in the entrepreneurial activities.

They are:

There should be a nonstop effort to inspire, encourage, motivate and co-operate women entrepreneurs.

Conduct the Awareness programme on a mass scale with the intention of creating awareness among women to conduct business. Organize training program for women entrepreneurs Vocational training to be extended to women community that is used to understand the production process and production management.

Skill development to be done in women's universities and industrial training institutes. The Educational institutes should tie up with various government and non-government agencies to assist in women entrepreneurship development. Banks and other institutions agencies are adopting special schemes for translation help women entrepreneurs.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneurs are the women who think of a enterprise. Women entrepreneurs are both about the women's position in society and about the role of entrepreneurship in the same society. Women participation in the field of entrepreneurship is increasing at large rate of hard work are taken at the company as well as global level to improve women participation in the enterprise sector. Countryside women are having basic original knowledge, skill, potential and resources to start and manage enterprise. But Indian society is male-dominated and the women are not treated as equal to men in inside and outside of four walls of the house. But now a days situation are change, the government takes many actions to help women entrepreneur.

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